

Impact of mechanical and chemical weeding on the floristic diversity of citrus orchards in Tlemcen (Northwestern of Algeria)

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to evaluate the impact of weeding on the floristic composition of citrus orchards in the region of Tlemcen (Northwestern of Algeria) where inappropriate management of weeds is practiced while they have a utility in the agroecosystems. A comparative approach between two methods of weeding (mechanical and chemical) compared to a control (without weeding) was carried out respectively at 03 stations of 100 m² in the citrus orchard studied on the one hand and on the other hand, before and after each weeding.

Concerning the floristic inventory, 168 surveys were carried out where 88 species were identified belonging to 71 genera and 29 botanical families. This remarkable adventitious flora is dominated by the Mediterranean elements (64%), the therophytes (51%) and dicotyledonous (64%). The statistical approach of the floristic data with the *R* software revealed, according to the applied treatment, the existence of a significant spatial-temporal difference in the mean species richness between the stations. In addition, the species richness before weeding is significantly higher compared to that after weeding for both methods of weeding. Thus, given its ecological role in sustainable agriculture, this floristic diversity deserves a more reasonable management.

Keywords: Weed control, weeds, citrus orchards, ANOVA, agroecosystem, Tlemcen.

Impact du désherbage mécanique et chimique sur la diversité floristique des vergers d'agrumes dans la région de Tlemcen (Nord-Ouest, Algérie)

Résumé:

La présente étude a été menée afin d'évaluer l'impact du désherbage sur la composition floristique de l'enherbement des agrumeraies dans la région de Tlemcen (Nord-Ouest, Algérie) où l'on pratique une gestion inappropriée des adventices par rapport à leur utilité dans un agroécosystème. Ainsi, une comparaison entre deux modes de désherbage (mécanique et chimique) par rapport à un témoin (sans désherbage) a été réalisée respectivement au niveau de 03 stations de 100m² dans une parcelle agrumicole avant et après chaque intervention. Pour l'établissement de l'inventaire floristique, 168 relevés ont été réalisés où 88 espèces ont été identifiées appartenant à 71 genres et 29 familles botaniques.

Cette remarquable flore adventice est dominée par les éléments méditerranéens (64%), les thérophytes (51%) et les dicotylédones (64%). L'approche statistique des données floristiques avec le logiciel R a révélé selon le traitement appliqué l'existence d'une différence spatio-temporelle importante dans la richesse moyenne en espèces entre les stations. Ainsi, compte tenu de son rôle écologique dans une agriculture durable, cette large diversité floristique mérite une gestion plus raisonnable.

Mots clés : Désherbage, adventices, agrumeraie, ANOVA, agroécosystème, Tlemcen.

Introduction

The repeated use of herbicides and the mechanical weeding engenders resistance of the weeds and considerably disturbs the role of the pedo-fauna in the biofertilistaion. Weeds are the most damaging bio-aggressor in terms of yield, in addition to the technical problems associated with their presence [1]. These problems are related to the evolution of the adventitious flora under the pressure of cultural techniques [2]. However, these weeds can be a biodiversity index and also a host to auxiliaries [3]. Good management of the adventitious flora certainly depends on a good knowledge of this flora and the species that compose it. For this purpose, several studies have been conducted in different regions in Algeria [4-6]. The presence of a weed is both related to an ecological environment (soil, climate) and agronomic (cultural practices). It is through the change of this environment that we can attempt to quantify the impacts on agriculture [7]. Changing agricultural practices influence the composition and evolution of weed communities [8, 9]. The impact of man on the weed communities is at the origin of the disappearance of the characteristic species of the poor environments (oligotrophiles) in favor of nitrophilic species; the disappearance of specialist species in relation to generalist species and the massive decline in species and species diversity affecting even common species [10].

Several management strategies have been developed. Among which, that of Bertrand and Doré [11], who discussed the control of weed flora through an integrated production system. Chauvel and *al.*, [12] also studied the integrated management of weed flora, which greatly limited the use of herbicide treatments, thus contributing to the control of the seed stock of weeds. Quennesson and Oste [13] have worked on weed management through soil cover by exploiting allelopathy and plant competition relationships for resources.

The objective of this work is to study the adventitious flora associated with citrus orchards and to compare the impacts of mechanical and chemical weeding on its floristic composition compared to a control without weeding.

Materials and methods

Presentation of the study area

Located on latitude 34 ° 58'19"N, longitude 01 ° 20'36"W and elevation 364m (Figure 1), the study area is part of the plain of Hennaya in the agricultural basin of the region of Tlemcen (North-West, Algeria) where citrus cultivation predominates. The climate of this region is

Mediterranean, semi-arid with moderate winter under a semi-continental influence and with a seasonal regime of precipitation of the HPAE type (winter, spring, autumn, summer). The dominant soils are brown, with a loamy to sandy-loamy texture, balanced, low in organic matter, and slightly alkaline with a low P₂O₅ reserve.

Experimental protocol

According to the minimal area recommended by Sorensen [14] to study perennial crops, three stations of 100m² were chosen inside the experimental plot (figure 1). They were subjected to mechanical weeding (M = y : 34.972006° ; x :-1.343233°), chemical weeding (C= y : 34.972580° ; x : -1.342573) and control without weeding (Ct= y : 34.971189° ; x : -1.343983°), respectively. The floristic surveys were carried out in each station according to the method described by Braun-Blanquet [15] and Guinochet [16] before and after each weeding.

The experimental approach was designed to compare two weed control methods against a control without weeding, where each species encountered was assigned a presence-absence index. A total of 168 surveys were conducted during the period from August 2016 to September 2017.

Systematic approach

New flora of Algeria and southern desert regions [17], the portable flora of France, Switzerland and Belgium [18], flora and vegetation of the Sahara [19, 20] and the flora of cultivated fields [21] were used for the identification, chorology determination and biological spectrum of inventoried species

Statistical analysis

In order to evaluate the impact of the method of weeding on the weed flora, the collected data were statistically processed (ANOVA) using the R software. Each species was codified by the first three letters of the genus, the first two letters of the species, and a number was assigned to each floristic surveys.

Results and discussion

Floristic composition

From the 168 floristic surveys conducted in citrus orchards, 88 species have been inventoried. All the species encountered are angiosperms, including 8 families, 23 genera and 32 monocotyledonous species, 21 families, 48 genera and 56 dicotyledonous species (Figure 2).

The 88 species belong to 71 genera and 29 botanical families. This number of families accounts for 73.29% of the weed flora of phytogeographic crops Oranais and 75.69% of the adventitious agrosystems flora of eastern Morocco. *Poaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Apiaceae* and *Fabaceae* are the most dominant families (Table 1). These four botanical families alone capitalize more than half of the species encountered a rate of 54.52%. Some families were accidentally encountered such as *Palmaceae*, *Oleaceae*, *Moraceae* and *Orchideae* (Table 1).

Ethological spectrum

Raunkiaer [23, 24] proposed the bases for a biological classification of plants. The criterion of bud position during the most unfavorable season to the plant remains in the case of weeds the basic criterion of a biological classification [21].

The ethological spectrum established for all species is mentioned in Figure 3, where therophytes are majority and represent 51.13% of the inventoried flora. This contribution is comparable to that established for citrus flora in eastern Morocco [22] and, for that reported by Kazi Tani et al., [6], respectively 69.3% and 75.52%.

Despite the importance of therophytes, hemicryptophytes occupy an important place (21.59%) and geophytes rank third with a contribution of 17.04% of the total inventoried species. The phanerophytes, chamaephytes and nanophanerophytes represent respectively 4.54%, 3.40% and 2.27% (Figure 3). In the same context, the perturbation index calculated by Loisel and Gamila [25] makes it possible to quantify the therophytization of a medium by the following formula:

$$P = [(Number\ of\ Chamephytes + Number\ of\ Therophytes) / Total\ number\ of\ species]$$

For the study area, the perturbation index is of the order of 54.54%. Therefore, the study area is almost half conserved, tending to a medium still in equilibrium with the biotic and abiotic conditions of the environment.

Biogeographic distribution

The phytogeographic study is an essential basis for any attempt to conserve biodiversity [26]. It represents a true model of interpretation of the phenomena of regressions [27]. Regarding to the chorology, the weed flora of Tlemcen citrus groves consists of heterogeneous elements of various origins: Mediterranean, northern and southern (Table 2).

Species with Mediterranean distribution sensu lato (including bi-regional and tri-regional) have a contribution of 63.63% (Table 2). This rate is close to that obtained by [6], for weed communities of phytogeographic crops Oranais of which 57.64% of the taxa are Mediterranean, 52% for perennial crops in the Mitidja plain [28], 59.01% for the weeds of eastern Morocco [22], and 62,3% for the weed flora of western Morocco agrosystems [29]. As for the endemic elements of North Africa, they are represented by a single species (*Pistacia atlantica* Desf.), which represents 1.13% of the total flora. For Algerian endemics, there is also a single species (*Hedysarum naudinianum* Coss.).

Statistical results

The results obtained by analyzing the two parameters time (before and after weeding) and the method of weeding (C, M and Ct) for the three stations showed that the richness of species differs between stations according to the weeding applied. : C with respect to the other two M and Ct (Figure 4). In fact, 81% of the inventoried species were present in the control station (Ct), 56% in the station with mechanical weeding and 43% in the chemical weeding station. From the point of view of time, the species richness before weeding is much higher compared to that after weeding for the two methods of weeding. A graphical representation using the R software allowed us to identify the spatio-temporal change in the mean species richness (Figure 4).

A factorial design is an experimental design in which the simultaneous study of two or more independent variables (factors) is performed in the same experiment in order to know the proper role of each independent variable, their relative importance, and their interaction. Since the level of significance of F-test is less than 0.01 (Table 3), this indicates that there are very significant differences between the three stations subjected to different weeding methods. The floristic composition encountered is significantly different for our experimental work. There is a very significant difference for the typology of the three stations, which reveals the impact of the weeding mode on the floristic composition of the weed flora of citrus groves.

At the level of the chemical weeding station, we recorded the presence of perennial weeds in favor of annuals. The majority of perennials are located in the basin irrigation. Paradoxically, annual weeds dominates in the station subjected to mechanical weeding

The species-plot interactions confirm the dissimilarity of the species richness and nature of the species recorded in the three stations, including their frequency of occurrence (Table 3). The species predominantly present in all floristic surveys were: *Oxalis pescaprae* L.,

Convolvulus arvensis L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. and *Cyperus rotundus* L. Otherwise several species were indifferent to the method of weeding and were present in the three station of the experimental plot (*Solanum nigrum* L., *Malva sylvestris* L., *Avena sterilis* L., *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Daucus carota* L., *Fumaria capreolata* L., *Portulaca oleracea* L. and *Setaria viridis* (L.) P. B.).

About the species-plot interaction and time, it turns out that the difference is really significant with a p-value (0.0000038) (Table 3). As a result, the method of weeding has an influence on the floristic diversity and the time of the highlighting.

In modern agriculture, chemical weeding of major crops has become a routine part of cropping techniques. Various socio-economic and environmental reasons nowadays call for an increased rationalization of chemical weed control in order to avoid as much as possible the treatments that have proved useless or superfluous. At the plot scale, any weed control program should be considered depending on the risk of weed damage to crop plants and potential damage to crop harvesting. However, any weed control program must be part of a technical farming itinerary and is planned in economic terms, whereas the weed nuisance is evaluated using experimental data measured in population biology in an environment artificially created by the man (the agrosystem) where he is advised to manage weeds for useful purposes as service plants.

Thus, in this state of mind, high crop productivity requires control and proper use of weeds [30]. But weed control in recent decades has led to the intensive use of herbicides that cause serious pollution problems and damage to biodiversity [31]. Chemical fertilizers are the main factors in maintaining soil fertility, but greater application with inadequate management reduces the availability of soil organic matter [32] and reduces the number of weeds [33]. In the face of this degradation of the natural resources "soil and plant species", many developing countries have to rethink their management methods while restricting the use of herbicides and promotion of agroecosystems [34]. The presence of weeds in cultivated crops can affect the production and quality of the crop by competing for light, moisture, nutrients and space [35] but can also be a not insignificant utility if they are taken into consideration. On the other hand, many studies indicate that weed diversity can have positive impacts on the functioning of agroecosystems [36, 33 and 37].

Moreover, in the cultivation of citrus, weeds rarely pose problems except on young plantations and adult citrus trees are not very sensitive to weeds. As a perspective, we are looking for studying the biological properties of weeds for the purpose of valorization of these species that can be exploited in the pharmaceutical industry.

Conclusion

The objective of this study is to evaluate the impact of mechanical and chemical weeding on the citrus-associated floristic diversity. The floristic surveys carried out during 2016-2017 have identified 88 species belonging to different botanical families. The weed flora of citrus groves is influenced by agricultural practices, including the method of weeding that affects its composition and the frequency of species that compose it. In general, four species occupy the first places; they are also the most common perennial weeds in Algeria: they are *Oxalis pescaprae* L., *Convolvulus arvensis* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. and *Cyperus rotundus* L. In this context, the notion of biological type is to be mentioned because in agronomy, the biological type is closely related to the cultural itinerary. The superficial and irregular tillage favors the installation of perennial weeds, whereas the therophytes are adapted to the productive and disturbed habitats because they are the only ones capable to growing between two tillage operations. As a result, the weed flora is subject to the pressure of farming techniques, as well as its composition, evolution and dynamics.

It should be noted that the impact of the weed control method on the floristic diversity of citrus orchards cannot be the only factor governing the floristic composition and the dynamics of the adventitious flora. Other agricultural practices may have an effect and need to be studied. In a global vision, it is now important to see that weeds can provide ecosystem services [38] even if they remain difficult to estimate and deserves further research in the future. Finally, this study has contributed to the consideration of the importance of the choice of weed management method but it requires other more precise studies. We recommend continuing the study for at least three years to see if there is reproducibility, expand the study area and complete the present study with an inquiry into the current situation of citrus growing in Algeria on all plans, and more specifically on the use of chemical inputs.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Références

- [1]. Labreuche, J., Laurent, F. and Roger-Estrade, J., 2014. Faut-il travailler le sol? Acquis et innovations pour une agriculture durable [*Do we need to work the soil? Acquired and innovative for sustainable agriculture*]. Edition Quae.
- [2]. Maillet, J., 1981. Evolution de la flore adventice dans le montpelliérais sous la pression des techniques culturales [Evolution of stands in Montpellier under the pressure of cultural techniques]. Montpellier: Université des Sciences et Techniques du Languedoc.
- [3]. Colbach, N., Biju-Duval, L., Gardarin, A., Granger, S., Guyot, S.H.M., Meziere D, Munier-Jolain, N.M. and Petit, S., 2014. The role of models for multicriteria evaluation and multiobjective design of cropping systems for managing weeds. *Weed research* **54**(6), 541-555.
- [4]. Abdelkrim, H., 2004. Contribution à l'étude écologique et phytosociologique des adventices des cultures et des jachères dans le secteur phytogéographique de l'Algérois (Algérie) [Contribution to the ecological and phytosociological study of weeds of crops and fallow land in the phytogeographic sector of algerois (Algeria)]. *Phytocoenologia* **34**(2), 287-326.
- [5]. Hannachi, A. and Fenni, M., 2013. Etude floristique et écologique des mauvaises herbes des cultures de la région de Batna (Algérie) [Floristic and ecological study of weeds from crops in the Batna's region (Algeria)]. *Revue Agriculture* **5**, 24-36.
- [6]. Kazi Tani, C., Le Bourgeois, T. and Munoz, F., 2010. Contribution à l'étude des communautés d'adventices des cultures du secteur phytogéographique Oranais (nord-ouest algérien): aspects botanique, agronomique et phyto-écologique [Contribution to the study of weed communities of phytogeographic crops Oranais (northwestern Algeria): botanical, agronomic and phyto-ecological aspects]. *Flora Mediterranea* **20**, 29-46.
- [7]. Fried, G., Chauvel, B. and Reboud, X., 2008. Evolution de la flore adventice des champs cultivés au cours des dernières décennies: vers la sélection de groupes d'espèces répondant aux systèmes de culture [Evolution of the adventitious flora of the cultivated fields in recent decades: towards the selection of groups of species responding to the systems of cultivation]. *Innovations Agronomiques* **3**, 15-26.
- [8]. Chafik, Z., Bouchache, M., Taleb, A. and Berrichi, A., 2014. Actualisation de la flore adventice des cépages du périmètre irrigué de la Moulouya [Updating the adventice flora of the grape varieties of the irrigated perimeter of the Moulouya]. *Revue Marocaine de Protection des Plantes* (5), 47-65.
- [9]. Fried, G. and Reboud, X., 2007. Évolution de la composition des communautés adventices des cultures de colza sous l'influence des systèmes de culture [Evolution of

- the composition of grassland communities of rapeseed crops under the influence of cropping systems]. *Oléagineux, Corps gras, Lipides* **14**(2), 130-138.
- [10]. Fried, G., 2010. Variations spatiales et temporelles des communautés adventices des cultures annuelles en France [Spatial and temporal variations in the adventitious communities of annual crops in France]. *Acta Botanica Gallica*, **157**(1), 183-192.
- [11]. Bertrand M, Doré T., 2008. Comment intégrer la maîtrise de la flore adventice dans le cadre général d'un système de production intégrée [How to integrate adventitious flora management into the overall framework of an integrated production system]. *Innovations Agron* **3**, 1-13.
- [12]. Chauvel, B., Tschudy, C. and Munier-Jolain, N., 2011. Gestion intégrée de la flore adventice dans les systèmes de culture sans labour [Integrated management of weed flora in no-till systems]. *Cahiers Agricultures* **20**(3), 194-203.
- [13]. Quennesson S, Oste S., 2017. Gestion des adventices par la couverture végétale du sol en agriculture et espaces verts : panorama de techniques utilisées [Weeds management by soil cover in agriculture and green spaces: an overview of techniques used]. In: *6^{ème} Conférence sur les moyens alternatifs de protection pour une production intégrée. Lille – 21, 22 et 23 mars 2017*. Edited by AFPP.
- [14]. Sorensen T., 1948. A method of establishing groups of equal amplitude in plant sociology based on similarity of species content. *Der Kong Danske Vidensk Selk Biol Ski (Copenhagen)* **5**(4), 1-34.
- [15]. Braun-Blanquet J., 1951. *Pflanzensoziologie Grundzuge der végétations* [Plant Sociology Fundamentals of the végétations], vol. 2. (Autriche: Kunde (2^{ème} Ed) Springer, Vienne, Ed.).
- [16]. Guinochet, M., 1973. *Phytosociologie* [Phytosociology]. (Paris: Masson Éd.).
- [17]. Quézel, P. and Santa, S., 1962-1963. *Nouvelle flore de l'Algérie et des régions désertiques méridionales* [New flora of Algeria and southern desert regions]. vol. 1-2. (Paris: CNRS).
- [18]. Bonnier, G., Hansson, A. and Skjervold, H., 1948. Studies on monozygous cattle twins. The interplay of heredity and environment on growth and yield. *Acta agriculturae Suecana* **3**, 1-57.
- [19]. Ozenda P., 1991. *Flore et végétation du Sahara* [Flora and vegetation of the Sahara]. (Paris: CNRS).
- [20]. Ozenda P., 1994. *Végétation du continent européen* [Vegetation of the European continent]. Delachaux et Niestlé.
- [21]. Jauzein, P., 2011. *Flore des champs cultivés* [The Flora of Cultivated Fields]. (Versailles : Quae Ed.).
- [22]. Chafik, Z., Taleb, A., Bouhache, M. and Berrichi, A., 2013. Flore adventice des agrosystèmes du Maroc Oriental: Cas du périmètre de la Moulouya [Weed flora of eastern Morocco agrosystems : Case of the Moulouya peremiter]. *Revue Marocaine de Protection des Plantes* **4**, 27-44.
- [23]. Raunkiaer CC., 1905. Types biologiques pour la géographie botanique [Biological types for botanical geography]. *Bull Acad, Rech Danemark* **5**, 347-437.
- [24]. Raunkiaer CC., 1934. The life forms of plants and statistical plant geography. *Being the collected papers of C Raunkiaer*.
- [25]. Loisel, R. and Gamila, H., 1993. Traduction des effets du débroussaillage sur les écosystèmes forestiers et préforestiers par un indice de perturbation [Translating the effects of brush removal on forest and pre-forest ecosystems by a disturbance index]. *Ann Soc Sci Nat Arch Toulon du Var*, pp: 123-132.
- [26]. Quézel, P., Barbero, M., Bonin, G. and Loisel, R., 1991. Pratiques agricoles et couvert forestier en région méditerranéenne humide et sub-humide [Agricultural practices and

- forest cover in the humid and sub-humid Mediterranean region]. vol. 1152. Univ. Aix-(Marseille III. Saint-Jérôme: UA. CNRS).
- [27]. Olivier, L., Muracciole, M. and Reduron, J-P., 1995. Premiers bilans sur la flore des îles de la Méditerranée. État des connaissances et conservation [First assessments on the flora of the Mediterranean islands. State of knowledge and conservation]. *Ecologia Mediterranea*, **21**, 355-372.
- [28]. Kheddam, M. and Adane, N., 1996. Contribution à l'étude phytoécologique des mauvaises herbes des cultures pérennes dans la plaine de la Mitidja. 2. Aspect écologique [Contribution to the phytoecological study of weeds of perennial crops in the plain of the Mitidja. 2. Ecological aspect]. *Annales Agronomiques* **17**(1-2), 1-26.
- [29]. Zidane, L., Salhi, S., Fadli, M., El Antri, M., Taleb, A. and Douira, A., 2010. Etude des groupements d'adventices dans le Maroc occidental [Study of weed groups in Western Morocco]. *Biotechnologie, Agronomie, Société et Environnement* **14**(1), 153-166.
- [30]. Siyahpoosh A, Fathi GA, Zand E, Siadat Sa, Bakhshande A, Gharineh MH. 2012. Competitiveness of different densities of two wheat cultivars with wild mustard weed species (*Sinapis arvensis*) in different densities. *World Applied Sciences Journal* **20**(5), 748-752.
- [31]. Zhang SZ, Li YH, Kong CH, Xu XH. 2015. Interference of allelopathic wheat with different weeds.
- [32]. Galal TM, Shehata HS. 2015. Impact of nutrients and heavy metals capture by weeds on the growth and production of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) irrigated with different water sources. *Ecological Indicators* **54**, 108–115.
- [33]. Franke AC, Lotz LAP, Van Der Burg WJ, Van Overbeek L. 2009. The role of arable weed seeds for agroecosystem functioning. *Weed Research* **49**, 131-141.
- [34]. Olesen JE, Hansen PK, Berntsen J, Christensen S. 2004. Simulation of above-ground suppression of competing species and competition tolerance in winter wheat varieties. *Field Crops Research* **89**, 263–280.
- [35]. Ashenafi M, Dalga D. 2014. Effect of herbicides on weed dynamics and yield and yield attribute of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in south eastern part of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Technology Advancing and Emerging Engineering Research* **2**(4), 2347-4289.
- [36]. Albrecht H., 2003. Suitability of arable weeds as indicator organisms to evaluate species conservation effects of management in agricultural ecosystems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* **98** (2003), 201-211.
- [37]. Norris RF, Kogan M., 2005. Ecology of interactions between weeds and arthropods. *Annual Review of Entomology* **50**, 479-503.
- [38]. Marshall E.J.P, Brown V.K, Boatman N.D, Lutman P.J.W, Squire G.R, Ward L.K., 2003. The role of weeds in supporting biological diversity within crop fields. *Weed Research* **43**, 77-89.

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Légende (C: Chemical weeding; M: Mechanical weeding; Ct: Control).

Figure 1. Situation and location of the study area.

Figure 2. Floristic composition of the study area.

Figure 3. Global ethological spectrum of weeds.

Legend (C: Chemical weeding, M: Mechanical weeding, Ct: Control, PA: Presence/Absence).

Figure 4. Spatio-temporal evolution of species richness according to treatment.

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Table 1. Total distribution of botanical families according to their specific contribution.

Botanical families	Genera	Species	Contribution (%)
<i>Poaceae</i>	12	19	21.59
<i>Asteraceae</i>	10	14	15.9
<i>Apiaceae</i>	9	9	10.22
<i>Fabaceae</i>	6	6	6.81
<i>Liliaceae</i>	4	4	4.54
<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>	2	3	3.4
<i>Cyperaceae</i>	1	3	3.4
<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	1	2	2.27
<i>Malvaceae</i>	1	2	2.27
<i>Orchideae</i> *	2	2	2.27
<i>Polygonaceae</i>	2	2	2.27
<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	1	2	2.27
<i>Labiataeae</i>	2	2	2.27
<i>Solanaceae</i>	2	2	2.27
<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Primulaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Araceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Aristolochiaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Boraginaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Geraniaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Moraceae</i> *	1	1	1.13
<i>Fumariaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Iridaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Araliaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Oleaceae</i> *	1	1	1.13
<i>Oxalidaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Portulacaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Rubiaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Brassicaceae</i>	1	1	1.13
<i>Palmaceae</i> *	1	1	1.13

Legend : * *Accidental families*

Table 2. Biogeographic origin of weeds and their contribution.

Geographic origin	Number of species	Contribution %
Mediterranean	30	34.09
Cosmopolitan	6	6.81
European-Mediterranean	5	5.68
Mediterranean-Iranian-Turanian	4	4.54
Atlantic-Mediterranean	4	4.54
Sub-cosmopolitan	3	3.40
Eurasian	3	3.40
Paleo-Subtropical	3	3.40
Paleo-Temperate	3	3.40
Mediterranean Circum	2	2.27
Ibero-Moroccan	2	2.27
Eastern Mediterranean	2	2.27
Western Mediterranean	2	2.27
Thermo cosmopolitan	2	2.27
Temperate-Subtropical	2	2.27
Macaronesian-Mediterranean	1	1.13
Mediterranean-Asian	1	1.13
Submediterranean	1	1.13
Spain-North Africa	1	1.13
Eurasiatic- Mediterranean	1	1.13
Tropical-Subtropical	1	1.13
Endemic	1	1.13
Circumboreal	1	1.13
West Mediterranean-Subatlantic	1	1.13
South African	1	1.13
Endemic. North African	1	1.13
European-Siberian-Mediterranean	1	1.13
European-Asian-North American	1	1.13
Macaronesian-Mediterranean-Iranian-Turanian	1	1.13
North tropical	1	1.13

Table 3. Multi-factor ANOVA (Response: Presence / Absence).

	Presence/Absence				
	Sumsq	DF	F value	Pr (>F)	Code
Species	90.5	87	26.1716	< 2.2e-16	***
Plot	0.64	2	8.0620	0.0003167	***
Time	0.14	1	3.4075	0.0649198	NS
Species : Plot	12.25	174	1.7708	0.000000002172	***
Species : Time	16.67	87	4.8204	< 2.2e-16	***
Plot : Time	0.02	2	0.1969	0.8212916	NS
Species : Plot: Time	10.79	174	1.5599	0.000003800582	***

NS = Not significant; * = Significant ** = Highly significant; *** = Very highly significant at 5% probability level, 1% and 1‰ respectively.